

**AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
TOURISM MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT
REPORT
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Index

1. TITLE: HOSTEL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM	-----
2. INTRODUCTION	-----
3. REQUIREMENT SPECIFICATION	-----
3.1: Hardware Requirements	-----
3.2: Software Requirements	-----
4. SYSTEM DESIGN	-----
4.1: Architecture	-----
4.2: UML Diagrams	-----
4.2.1: Use Case	-----
4.2.2: Entity-Relationship	-----
4.2.3: Class	-----
4.2.4: Activity	-----
4.2.5: Component	-----
4.3: DFD	-----
5. SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION	-----
6. RESULTS	-----
6.1: Tables	-----
6.2: Test Case	-----
6.3: Reports	-----
6.4: Screenshots	-----
7. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE	-----
8. REFERENCE	-----

1. TITLE

Tourism Management System

PROPOSED SYSTEM:

The proposed system is a web based application and maintains a centralized repository of all related information. The proposed system maintains centralized repository to make necessary travel arrangements and to retrieve information easily.

The system allows one to easily access the relevant information and make necessary travel arrangements. Users can decide about places they want to visit and make bookings online for travel and accommodation.

The tourism management system allows the user of the system access all the details such as weather, location, events, etc. The main purpose is to help tourism companies to manage customer and hotels etc. The system can also be used for both professional and business trips.

This particular project deals with the problems on managing a tour and avoids the problems which occur when carried manually.

1. INTRODUCTION

Travel and Tourism management system is an online project to provide the complete information about the vehicles available for a tour. There are 2 different types of users. First the customer visits the site and enters the place from where to where he wishes to travel. He also provides the date as when he would like to travel. Then he sends these details to the travel and tourism agency. The employee of travel and tourism agency receives the mail and check which vehicle is available for that day and reverts back to the customer along with the quotation.

If the customer agrees for any one of the quotation, he can reply back along with agreed quotation. Then the agency will take down all the details of the customer and will send a confirmation message to the customer. On the day of the tour, the customer first must show the confirmation message to the driver for clarity and only then he will agree to drive after looking at the confirmation message. This software is user friendly and helps in finding the vehicle sooner rather than wandering manually everywhere to find for vehicles. Before the tour starts, half payment has to be done.

After the customer returns or reaches his final destination, he must pay full amount either through cash or through cards. After the travelling the customer can come back to the site and enter his feedback about the travel and tourism agency. If any good feedback will be taken positively and if any negative feedback too will be taken positively and try to improve what had lacked. The report is also generated periodically and the database will be cleared according to the time.

OBJECTIVE:

The objective of the Travel and Tourism Management System project is to develop a system that automates the processes and activities of a travel and the purpose is to design a system using which one can perform all operations related to traveling.

APPLICATIONS

This application is built such a way that it should suits for all type of blood banks in future. So every effort is taken to implement this project in this blood bank, on successful implementation in this blood bank, we can target other blood banks in the city.

This application consists following modules

Administrator module:

This module provides administrator related functionality. Administrator manages all information and has access rights to add, delete, edit and view the data related to places, travels, routes, bookings, restaurants etc.

Travels module:

This module provides the details of various travel agencies. A user can select the appropriate agency depending on convenience and accessibility.

Routes module:

This module provides information related to various routes connecting sources and destinations. For each route, information such as source, destination, fare, reservation details, pick up points etc are provides. Only administrator can add , delete, edit and manage the data. Users can only view the information.

Reservations module:

This module provides functionalities that allow a user to book tickets or cancel previously booked tickets. The module maintains the details of all reservations made so far and allows administrator to either confirm or reject the bookings.

Testimonials module:

Users of this application can post their opinions, complaints and suggestions regarding this portal and services to the administrator. Accordingly, the administrator can take various steps to act on the complaints and suggestions.

REQUIREMENT SPECIFICATION

A major element in building a system is the section of compatible software since the software in the market is experiencing in geometric progression. Selected software should be acceptable by the firm and one user as well as it should be feasible for the system.

Hardware Requirement:

Processor	:	Intel Core Duo 2.0 GHz or more
RAM	:	1 GB or More
Hard disk	:	80GB or more
Monitor	:	15" CRT, or LCD monitor
Keyboard	:	Normal or Multimedia
Mouse	:	Compatible mouse

Software Requirement:

Front End	:	ASP.net with C# as scripting language XAMPP CONSOLE.
Back End	:	Microsoft SQL Server2008
Operation System	:	Windows XP,7,8,10

SYSTEM DESIGN

USE Case Diagram:

ER Diagram:

Activity Diagram:

Component Diagram:

DATA FLOW DIAGRAM:

ADMIN Dashboard:

SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

Codes for Homepage:

```
<?php
session_start();
error_reporting(0);
include('includes/config.php');
?>
<!DOCTYPE HTML>
<html>
<head>
<title>TMS | Tourism Management System</title>
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />

<script type="applijewelleryion/x-javascript"> addEventListener("load", function() {
setTimeout(hideURLbar, 0); }, false); function hideURLbar(){ window.scrollTo(0,1); } </script>

<link href="css/bootstrap.css" rel='stylesheet' type='text/css' />
<link href="css/style.css" rel='stylesheet' type='text/css' />
<link href="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Open+Sans:400,700,600" rel='stylesheet' type='text/css'>
<link href="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Roboto+Condensed:400,700,300" rel='stylesheet'
type='text/css'>
<link href="//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Oswald" rel='stylesheet' type='text/css'>
<link href="css/font-awesome.css" rel="stylesheet">
<!-- Custom Theme files -->
<script src="js/jquery-1.12.0.min.js"></script>
<script src="js/bootstrap.min.js"></script>
<!--animate-->
<link href="css/animate.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" media="all">
```

```
<script src="js/wow.min.js"></script>

<script>
new WOW().init();
</script>

<!--//end-animate-->

</head>

<body>

<?php include('includes/header.php');?>

<div class="banner">

<div class="container">

<h1 class="wow zoomIn animated animated" data-wow-delay=".5s" style="visibility: visible;
animation-delay: 0.5s; animation-name: zoomIn;"> TMS - Tourism Management System</h1>

</div>

</div>

<!-- rupes ---->

<div class="container">

<div class="rupes">

<div class="col-md-4 rupes-left wow fadeInDown animated animated" data-wow-delay=".5s"
style="visibility: visible; animation-delay: 0.5s; animation-name: fadeInDown;">

<div class="rup-left">

<a href="offers.html"><i class="fa fa-usd"></i></a>

</div>

<div class="rup-rgt">

<h3>UP TO 50% OFF</h3>

<h4><a href="offers.html">TRAVEL SMART</a></h4>

</div>

<div class="clearfix"></div>
```

</div>

<div class="col-md-4 rupes-left wow fadeInDown animated animated" data-wow-delay=".5s" style="visibility: visible; animation-delay: 0.5s; animation-name: fadeInDown;">

<div class="rup-left">

<i class="fa fa-h-square"></i>

</div>

<div class="rup-rgt">

<h3>UP TO 70% OFF</h3>

<h4>ON HOTELS ACROSS WORLD</h4>

</div>

<div class="clearfix"></div>

</div>

<div class="col-md-4 rupes-left wow fadeInDown animated animated" data-wow-delay=".5s" style="visibility: visible; animation-delay: 0.5s; animation-name: fadeInDown;">

<div class="rup-left">

<i class="fa fa-mobile"></i>

</div>

<div class="rup-rgt">

<h3>FLAT 40% OFF</h3>

<h4>US APP OFFER</h4>

</div>

<div class="clearfix"></div>

</div>

</div>

</div>

<!-- /rupes ---->

```

<!--holiday---->
<div class="container">
<div class="holiday">
<h3>Package List</h3>
<?php $sql = "SELECT * from tbltourpackages order by rand() limit 4";
$query = $dbh->prepare($sql);
$query->execute();
$results=$query->fetchAll(PDO::FETCH_OBJ);
$cnt=1;
if($query->rowCount() > 0)
{
foreach($results as $result)
{ ?>
<div class="rom-btm">
<div class="col-md-3 room-left wow fadeInLeft animated" data-wow-delay=".5s">
</div>
<div class="col-md-6 room-middle wow fadeInUp animated" data-wow-delay=".5s">
<h4>Package Name: <?php echo htmlentities($result->PackageName);?></h4>
<h6>Package Type : <?php echo htmlentities($result->PackageType);?></h6>
<p><b>Package Location :</b> <?php echo htmlentities($result->PackageLocation);?></p>
<p><b>Features</b> <?php echo htmlentities($result->PackageFetures);?></p>
</div>
<div class="col-md-3 room-right wow fadeInRight animated" data-wow-delay=".5s">
<h5>INR <?php echo htmlentities($result->PackagePrice);?></h5>
<a href="package-details.php?pkgid=<?php echo htmlentities($result->PackageId);?>"
class="view">Details</a>
</div>

```

```
<div class="clearfix"></div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<?php }} ?>
```

```
<div><a href="package-list.php" class="view">View More Packages</a></div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<div class="clearfix"></div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<!-- routes ---->
```

```
<div class="routes">
```

```
<div class="container">
```

```
<div class="col-md-4 routes-left wow fadeInRight animated" data-wow-delay=".5s">
```

```
<div class="rou-left">
```

```
<a href="#"><i class="glyphicon glyphicon-list-alt"></i></a>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<div class="rou-rgt wow fadeInDown animated" data-wow-delay=".5s">
```

```
<h3>80000</h3>
```

```
<p>Enquiries</p>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<div class="clearfix"></div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<div class="col-md-4 routes-left">
```

```
<div class="rou-left">
```

```
<a href="#"><i class="fa fa-user"></i></a>
```

```
</div>
```

```

<div class="rou-rgt">
<h3>1900</h3>
<p>Registered users</p>
</div>
<div class="clearfix"></div>
</div>
<div class="col-md-4 routes-left wow fadeInRight animated" data-wow-delay=".5s">
<div class="rou-left">
<a href="#"><i class="fa fa-ticket"></i></a>
</div>
<div class="rou-rgt">
<h3>7,00,00,000+</h3>
<p>Booking</p>
</div>
<div class="clearfix"></div>
</div>
<div class="clearfix"></div>
</div>
</div>
</body>
</html>

```

Codes for admin dashboard:

```

<?php
session_start();
include('includes/config.php');
if(strlen($_SESSION['alogin'])==0)

```

```
{
header('location:index.php');
}
else{
?>
<!DOCTYPE HTML>
<html>
<head>
<title>TMS | Admin Dashboard</title>
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />
<script type="application/x-javascript"> addEventListener("load", function() {
setTimeout(hideURLbar, 0); }, false); function hideURLbar(){ window.scrollTo(0,1); } </script>
<!-- Bootstrap Core CSS -->
<link href="css/bootstrap.min.css" rel='stylesheet' type='text/css' />
<!-- Custom CSS -->
<link href="css/style.css" rel='stylesheet' type='text/css' />
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/morris.css" type="text/css"/>
<!-- Graph CSS -->
<link href="css/font-awesome.css" rel="stylesheet">
<!-- jQuery -->
<script src="js/jquery-2.1.4.min.js"></script>
<!-- //jQuery -->
<link href='//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Roboto:700,500,300,100italic,100,400' rel='stylesheet'
type='text/css'/>
<link href='//fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Montserrat:400,700' rel='stylesheet' type='text/css'>
<!-- lined-icons -->
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/icon-font.min.css" type='text/css' />
```

```
<!-- //lined-icons -->
</head>
<body>
<div class="page-container">
<!--/content-inner-->
<div class="left-content">
<div class="mother-grid-inner">
<!--header start here-->
<?php include('includes/header.php');?>
<!--header end here-->
<ol class="breadcrumb">
<li class="breadcrumb-item"><a href="index.html">Home</a> <i class="fa fa-angle-right"></i></li>
</ol>
<!--four-grids here-->
<div class="four-grids">
<div class="col-md-3 four-grid">
<div class="four-agileits">
<div class="icon">
<i class="glyphicon glyphicon-user" aria-hidden="true"></i>
</div>
<div class="four-text">
<h3>User</h3>

<?php $sql = "SELECT id from tblusers";
$query = $dbh -> prepare($sql);
$query->execute();
$results=$query->fetchAll(PDO::FETCH_OBJ);
$cnt=$query->rowCount();
```

```
?> <h4> <?php echo htmlentities($cnt);?> </h4>
```

```
</div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<div class="col-md-3 four-grid">
```

```
<div class="four-agileinfo">
```

```
<div class="icon">
```

```
<i class="glyphicon glyphicon-list-alt" aria-hidden="true"></i>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<div class="four-text">
```

```
<h3>Bookings</h3>
```

```
<?php $sql1 = "SELECT BookingId from tblbooking";
```

```
$query1 = $dbh -> prepare($sql1);
```

```
$query1->execute();
```

```
$results1=$query1->fetchAll(PDO::FETCH_OBJ);
```

```
$cnt1=$query1->rowCount();
```

```
?>
```

```
<h4><?php echo htmlentities($cnt1);?></h4>
```

```
</div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<div class="col-md-3 four-grid">
```

```
<div class="four-w3ls">
```

```
<div class="icon">
<i class="glyphicon glyphicon-folder-open" aria-hidden="true"></i>
</div>
<div class="four-text">
<h3>Enquiries</h3>
<?php $sql2 = "SELECT id from tblequiry";
$query2= $dbh -> prepare($sql2);
$query2->execute();
$results2=$query2->fetchAll(PDO::FETCH_OBJ);
$cnt2=$query2->rowCount();
?>
<h4><?php echo htmlentities($cnt2);?></h4>
```

```
</div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<div class="col-md-3 four-grid">
```

```
<div class="four-wthree">
```

```
<div class="icon">
```

```
<i class="glyphicon glyphicon-briefcase" aria-hidden="true"></i>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<div class="four-text">
```

```
<h3>Toatal packages</h3>
```

```
<?php $sql3 = "SELECT PackageId from tbltourpackages";
```

```
$query3= $dbh -> prepare($sql3);
```

```
$query3->execute();
```

```
$results3=$query3->fetchAll(PDO::FETCH_OBJ);
```

```
$cnt3=$query3->rowCount();
?>
<h4><?php echo htmlentities($cnt3);?></h4>

</div>

</div>

</div>

<div class="clearfix"></div>

</div>

<div class="four-grids">
<div class="col-md-3 four-grid">
<div class="four-w3ls">
<div class="icon">
<i class="glyphicon glyphicon-folder-open" aria-hidden="true"></i>
</div>
<div class="four-text">
<h3>Issues Riased</h3>
<?php $sql5 = "SELECT id from tblissues";
$query5= $dbh -> prepare($sql5);
$query5->execute();
$results5=$query5->fetchAll(PDO::FETCH_OBJ);
$cnt5=$query5->rowCount();
?>
<h4><?php echo htmlentities($cnt5);?></h4>

</div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<div class="clearfix"></div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<!--//four-grids here-->
```

```
<div class="inner-block">
```

```
</div>
```

```
<!--inner block end here-->
```

```
<!--copy rights start here-->
```

```
<?php include('includes/footer.php');?>
```

```
</div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<!--/sidebar-menu-->
```

```
<?php include('includes/sidebarmenu.php');?>
```

```
<div class="clearfix"></div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<script>
```

```
var toggle = true;
```

```
$(".sidebar-icon").click(function() {
```

```
if (toggle)
```

```

{
$(".page-container").addClass("sidebar-collapsed").removeClass("sidebar-collapsed-back");
$("#menu span").css({"position":"absolute"});
}
else
{
$(".page-container").removeClass("sidebar-collapsed").addClass("sidebar-collapsed-back");
setTimeout(function() {
$("#menu span").css({"position":"relative"});
}, 400);
}

toggle = !toggle;
});
</script>
<!--js -->
<script src="js/jquery.nicescroll.js"></script>
<script src="js/scripts.js"></script>
<!-- Bootstrap Core JavaScript -->
<script src="js/bootstrap.min.js"></script>
<!-- /Bootstrap Core JavaScript -->
<!-- morris JavaScript -->
<script src="js/raphael-min.js"></script>
<script src="js/morris.js"></script>
<script>
$(document).ready(function() {
//BOX BUTTON SHOW AND CLOSE
jQuery('.small-graph-box').hover(function() {

```

```
jQuery(this).find('.box-button').fadeIn('fast');
}, function() {
jQuery(this).find('.box-button').fadeOut('fast');
});
jQuery('.small-graph-box .box-close').click(function() {
jQuery(this).closest('.small-graph-box').fadeOut(200);
return false;
});
```

```
//CHARTS
```

```
function gd(year, day, month) {
return new Date(year, month - 1, day).getTime();
}
```

```
graphArea2 = Morris.Area({
element: 'hero-area',
padding: 10,
behaveLikeLine: true,
gridEnabled: false,
gridLineColor: '#dddddd',
axes: true,
resize: true,
smooth:true,
pointSize: 0,
lineWidth: 0,
fillOpacity:0.85,
data: [
{period: '2014 Q1', iphone: 2668, ipad: null, itouch: 2649},
```

```
{period: '2014 Q2', iphone: 15780, ipad: 13799, itouch: 12051},
{period: '2014 Q3', iphone: 12920, ipad: 10975, itouch: 9910},
{period: '2014 Q4', iphone: 8770, ipad: 6600, itouch: 6695},
{period: '2015 Q1', iphone: 10820, ipad: 10924, itouch: 12300},
{period: '2015 Q2', iphone: 9680, ipad: 9010, itouch: 7891},
{period: '2015 Q3', iphone: 4830, ipad: 3805, itouch: 1598},
{period: '2015 Q4', iphone: 15083, ipad: 8977, itouch: 5185},
{period: '2016 Q1', iphone: 10697, ipad: 4470, itouch: 2038},
{period: '2016 Q2', iphone: 8442, ipad: 5723, itouch: 1801}
],
lineColors:['#ff4a43','#a2d200','#22beef'],
xkey: 'period',
redraw: true,
ykeys: ['iphone', 'ipad', 'itouch'],
labels: ['All Visitors', 'Returning Visitors', 'Unique Visitors'],
pointSize: 2,
hideHover: 'auto',
resize: true
});
```

```
});
```

```
</script>
```

```
</body>
```

```
</html>
```

```
<?php } ?>
```

6. RESULTS

6.1 Table Case :

Sr No.	Name	Gender	DOB	Address	PIN CODE	Contact No.
1	anuj	Male	08/10/1999	Koparkhairane	400709	123456789
2	sarita	female	23/05/1999	Ghansoli	400708	369765421
3	demo	Male	12/07/2000	Thane	400710	465686860
4	sameer	Male	16/05/2012	Vashi	400506	369745128

6.2 Test Case :

Test case no	Test	Expected output	Outcome
1	Admin login page logs into admin profile	YES	YES
2	Admin login logs into user profile	YES	YES
3	Admin can be add various places	YES	YES
4	Admin is able to see user's booking	YES	YES

SCREENSHOTS

MAIN HOME PAGE:

PACKAGES LIST:

ADMIN DASHBOARD:

REGISTRATION PAGE:

FUTURE SCOPE

- Tourism is growing and so is the scope in tourism increasing. There is a good employment in the tourism sector. Thus too grab such opportunities you need to prepare yourself with the knowledge in tourism.
- Any tourist agency can make use of it for saving customer details in database.
- Tourism group can use it for managing their location, hotel, vehicles details.
- This application can easily implemented under various situations.
- We can add new features as and when we require.
- Reusability of this application is also possible.

CONCLUSION

“Travel and tourism management” simplifies the management process in travelling.

- Fast processing and immediate results with high security.
- Minimizing human effort and cost efficient databases.
- Navigation through the site is easy.

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